

Hemicyanines. Part I

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Six hemicyanines have been prepared by condensing *p*-dimethyl- and *p*-diethyl-aminobenzaldehydes with 6-chloro-, 6-bromo-, and 6-iodo-quinazoline methiodides. The sensitisation and other properties of the dyes are reported.

Hemicyanines involving quinolines are generally known to be useful sensitisers. The literature¹ reports quite a large number of such dyes containing variously substituted quinoline nucleus. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the effect of halogen substituents at the 6-position of the quinoline nucleus in 2-*p*-dimethyl- and 2-*p*-diethyl-aminostyryl dyes.

Six new dyes have been prepared by condensing 6-chloro-, 6-bromo-, and 6-iodo-quinazoline methiodides with *p*-dimethyl- and *p*-diethyl-aminobenzaldehydes. The dyes obtained are represented as :

(I): X=Cl; R=Me.

(II): X=Br; R=Me.

(III): X=I; R=Me.

(IV): X=Cl; R=Et.

(V): X=Br; R=Et.

(VI): X=I; R=Et.

The quaternisation of the involved bases was effected by the usual method of heating the base in sealed tubes with the alkyl iodide in 1 : 1.5 molar proportions. The dyes were prepared by refluxing the requisite quaternised salt and the aldehyde in molar proportions in anhydrous ethanol with piperidine as catalyst.

1. Hamer, "The Cyanine Dyes and Related Compounds", Interscience Publishers, New York—London, 1964.

The dyes are highly crystalline and pleochroic and are soluble in alcohols, the colour of the solutions in ethanol being discharged by addition of mineral acids and regenerated on dilution or basification.

FIG. 1

Diethyl series: 6-I > 6-Cl > 6-Br.

Dimethyl series: 6-Cl > 6-Br, 6-I.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absorption was recorded on a Beckman DU model spectrophotometer. The sensitisation was recorded on an Adam Hilger Wedge spectrograph using a 150 C.P. a.c. Point-o-lite source. Ilford Process N. 40 plates were used. The plates were initially moistened for a minute in tepid water, drained, and then bathed for 5 min. in 1/100,000 solution of the dye in 66% ethanol. The bathed plates were drained and dried before exposure. Exposures of 3 min. were given and plates were developed as usual.

The absorption maxima and the ranges of extra-sensitisation are shown in Table I. The sensitisation spectra are reproduced in Fig. 1, the sensitisation spectrum of an unbathed process plate being appended for the sake of comparison.

The absorption maxima of the diethyl and dimethyl dyes are in the order: 6-I > 6-Br > 6-Cl.

The absorption maxima of the diethyl dyes are in all cases greater than their dimethyl analogues.

The ranges of extra-sensitisation conferred on gelatinised silver halide plate are in the order :

TABLE I

Dye No.	EtOH max.	Extro-sensitization [m μ].		Remarks.
		Range.	Maximum.	
I	548 m μ	520-650	595	Weak at 520-550.
II	660	520-660	595	..
III	552	520-650	600	Slightly weak at 520-550
IV	550	520-670	620	Weak at 520-550
V	560	520-650	600	Weak at 520-550
VI	564	520-672	630	..

Preparation of the Quaternised Salts

The bases and alkyl iodides (1:1.5 molar) were heated together in sealed tubes on a steam bath for 36 hr. The product was extracted repeatedly with hot water. The collected aqueous extracts on evaporation left a solid mass which was washed a few times with ether to remove any unchanged base. The salts were recrystallised from rectified spirit.

6-Chloroquinaldine Methiodide: Yield 56%; m.p. 211-12° (decomp). (Found: N, 4.36; Cl+I, 50.58. C₁₁H₁₁NClI requires N, 4.38; Cl+I, 50.86%).

6-Iodoquinaldine Methiodide: Yield 55%; m.p. 260°. (Found: N, 3.38; I, 61.62. C₁₁H₁₁NI₂ requires N, 3.40; I, 61.80%).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-chloroquinoline Methiodide (I).—6-Chloroquinaldine methiodide (0.64 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.3 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml) were refluxed with piperidine (4 drops) under a moisture trap for 15 min. The dye separating (0.55 g.) on cooling was recrystallised from methanol as dark shining crystals, m.p. 246°. (Found: N, 6.28; Cl+I, 35.87. C₂₀H₂₀N₂ClI requires N, 6.21; Cl+I, 36.07%).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-bromoquinoline Methiodide (II).—A mixture of 6-bromoquinaldine methiodide (0.55 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.22 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (35 ml) was gently refluxed with piperidine (4 drops) under a moisture trap for 1½ hr. The dye (0.44 g.) separating on cooling was recrystallised from methanol as dark shining crystals, m.p. 252°. (Found: N, 5.54; Br+I, 41.65. C₂₀H₂₀N₂BrI requires N, 5.65; Br+I, 41.81%).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-iodoquinoline Methiodide (III).—On refluxing 6-iodoquinaldine methiodide (0.62 g.) with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.22 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (105 ml) with piperidine (4 drops) under a moisture trap for 1½ hours, the dye separated (0.47 g.). It was recrystallised from methanol in dark shining needles, m.p. 266°. (Found: N, 5.08; I, 46.78. C₂₀H₂₀N₂I₂ requires N, 5.16; I, 46.86%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-chloroquinoline Methiodide (IV).—A mixture of 6-chloroquinaldine methiodide (0.96 g.) with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.5 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed with piperidine (4 drops) for an hour when the dye separated (0.82 g.). It was recrystallised from methanol in dark shining needles, m.p. 225° (decomp). (Found: N, 5.72; Cl+I, 33.72. C₂₂H₂₄N₂ClI requires N, 5.85; Cl+I, 33.96%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-bromoquinoline Methiodide(V).—0-Bromoquinaldine methiodide (0.55 g.) and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.3g.) in anhydrous ethanol (35 ml) were refluxed with piperidine (4 drops) for 1½ hr. The dye separating (0.43 g.) was recrystallised from methanol as dark red crystals, m.p. 227°(decomp.). (Found: N, 5.31; Br+I, 39.42. $C_{22}H_{24}N_2BrI$ requires N, 5.35; Br+I, 39.57%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-iodoquinaldine Methiodide(VI).—On refluxing 6-iodoquinaldine methiodide (0.62 g.) and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.27 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (195 ml) and piperidine (4 drops) for 1½ hr., the dye (0.62 g.) separated. It was recrystallised from methanol as dark fine crystals, m.p. 242°. (Found: N, 4.85; I, 44.37. $C_{22}H_{24}N_2I_2$ requires N, 4.91; I, 44.56%).

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